

Analysis of Evaluation of Implementation of Standard Precautions in Prevention and Control of Healthcare Associated Infections at the Kendari City Regional General Hospital in 2024

Esther Kendek Rost¹, Mubarak², Syawal Kamiluddin Saptaputra³, Arimaswati⁴

¹Master of Public Health Study Program, Postgraduate Program, Halu Oleo University Kendari, Indonesia

²Nursing Study Program, Faculty of Medicine, Halu Oleo University, Kendari, Indonesia

³Public Health Master's Study Program, Postgraduate Program, Halu Oleo University Kendari, Indonesia

⁴Medical Education Study Program, Faculty of Medicine, Halu Oleo University, Kendari, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: HAIs infections are infections that occur in patients during treatment in hospitals and other health care facilities where when they enter there is no infection and is not in the incubation period. Standard precautions in preventing infection are very important to apply in hospitals, considering that staff contact with patients' bodies increases exposure from patients to staff or vice versa. The research was conducted to evaluate the implementation of standard precautions in preventing and controlling HAIs infections in Kendari City Regional Public Houses in 2024. The research was conducted in the period from April to May 2024. All data that was collected was analyzed using a content analysis approach, namely comparing the research results with existing theories and a literature review. The research results show that hand hygiene has not been fully implemented by nurses in accordance with the 5 moments and 6 steps of hand washing. The use of PPE has been fully implemented by nurses, especially in the use of masks and gloves. Coughing and sneezing etiquette has not been fully implemented by nurses because nurses have not thrown tissues into infectious waste bins. Safe injection practices have not been fully implemented by all officers because there are still those who carry out recapping.

KEYWORDS: Evaluation, HAIs Infection, Standard Precautions.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, quality health services have become the world's spotlight. The quality of health services has become a demand from every level of society. In response to this, several countries have begun to develop various indicators related to the quality of health services, one of which is known as accreditation. Responding to the problem of hospital quality, various countries have formulated their policies regarding the accreditation process that applies to health service providers in their regions. In Indonesia itself, accreditation is an obligation that must be carried out by hospitals and is carried out every three years, as stated in Law no. 44 of 2009 concerning Hospitals [1]. This was then confirmed by the publication of regulations derived from this law, namely Minister of Health Regulation no. 12 of 2012 concerning Hospital Accreditation [2]. Hospital Accreditation Standards consist of several assessment indicators, one of which is patient safety targets [3].

A hospital is a health service institution that provides complete individual health services, providing inpatient, outpatient and emergency services [1]. Hospitals are also a source of various diseases, which originate from sufferers and visitors who are carriers. These disease germs live and develop in hospital environments, such as air, water, floors, food and medical and nonmedical equipment. So infections that are caused by influences from the hospital environment are called Healthcare Associated Infections (HAIs) [4].

Health care-associated infectious diseases (HAIs) are a health problem in various countries in the world, including Indonesia. HAIs are infections that occur in patients during treatment in hospitals and other health care facilities where when admitted there was no infection and was not in the incubation period, including infections in hospitals but appearing after the patient has gone home, as well as work-related infections in hospital staff and health workers related to the health service process in health care facilities [5]. HAIs are infections that are acquired while patients are undergoing treatment procedures and medical procedures at health care

facilities within 48 hours to 30 days and infections are observed after the patient leaves the health care facility. HAIs can prolong the length of patient care up to 4–5 days and can also be a cause of death in patients [6].

A survey conducted in 183 hospitals in the United States with 11,282 patients reported that 4% of patients were infected with at least one type of HAIs. In high-income countries, about 30% of patients in the ICU are infected with at least one type of HAIs. While in low- and middle-income countries, the frequency of infections acquired in the ICU is at least 2-3 times higher than in high-income countries. In Asian countries, the incidence of nosocomial infections occurs as much as 10%. while in America the incidence of nosocomial infections occurs in $\pm 5\%$ of the 40 million patients treated each year with a mortality rate of 1% and a treatment cost burden of 4.5 billion dollars per year. The prevalence of HAIs infection in patients in developed countries varies between 3.5% to 12%, while in developing countries including Indonesia, the prevalence of HAIs infection is 9.1% with a variation of 6.1%-16% [7].

According to data from the Ministry of Health, HAIs infections in Indonesia reached 15.74%, far above developed countries which range from 4-8-15.5% [8]. In 2003, Perdalin Jaya and Prof. Hospital. Dr. Sulianti Saroso conducted a survey of 11 hospitals in DKI Jakarta. Based on these results, data on the prevalence of nosocomial infections for Surgical Wound Infections (SSI) was 18.9%, Urinary Tract Infections (UTI) 15.1%, Primary Bloodstream Infections (IADP) 26.4%, Pneumonia 24.5% and other respiratory tract infections 15.1% and other infections 32.1% [9]. The types of HAIs that most often occur in health care facilities, especially hospitals include: Ventilator associated pneumonia (VAP), Bloodstream Infections (IAD), Urinary Tract Infections (UTI), Surgical Site Infections (SSI). In Indonesia, the incidence of infection in hospitals is around 3 – 21% (average 9%) or more than 1.4 million inpatients in hospitals throughout the world. According to [10] concluded that nosocomial infections are a significant cause of morbidity, mortality, prolonging patient care periods and increasing health service costs. The incidence of HAIs in hospitals can result in the quality of service being less than optimal, so appropriate action is needed to prevent and reduce the incidence of these infections.

In principle, the incidence of HAIs can actually be prevented if health care facilities consistently implement Infection Prevention and Control (PPI) programs. PPI is an effort to ensure protection for everyone against the possibility of contracting infections from sources in the general public and while receiving health services at various health facilities. With the development of science, especially in the field of health services, patient care is not only provided in hospitals but also in other health service facilities, even at home (home care). The existence of the PPI program in health service facilities aims to improve the quality of service in health service facilities, thereby protecting health human resources, patients and the community from infectious diseases related to health services [5].

To implement PPI in hospitals, a committee is needed to drive the implementation of PPI in the hospital. The PPI Committee is tasked with compiling, determining and evaluating PPI policies as well as carrying out socialization of PPI policies so that these policies can be understood and implemented by health workers. In addition, the PPI Committee creates Standard Operational Procedures for PPI and prepares the PPI program every year and evaluates its implementation. The PPI Committee also carries out investigations and proposes the procurement of tools and materials that comply with PPI principles and are safe for those who use them. The PPI Committee consists of the Committee Chair, Committee Secretary, full-time PPI nurse (IPCN), PPI Doctor (IPCO) and daily care nurse (IPCLN) [5]. The implementation of PPI in health service facilities aims to protect patients, health workers and visitors who receive health services as well as the community in their environment by breaking the cycle of infectious disease transmission through standard and transmission-based precautions [5].

Implementing standard precautions is expected to reduce the risk of pathogen transmission in the body from both known and unknown sources. This implementation is infection prevention and control that must be routinely implemented for all patients and all health care facilities [5]. Standard precautions that must be implemented in the care of all patients in hospitals to prevent infection include: hand hygiene, Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), decontamination of patient care equipment, environmental health, waste management, linen management, health protection of staff, patient placement, respiratory hygiene/coughing and sneezing etiquette, safe injection practices and safe lumbar puncture practices.

The results of initial data collection at the Kendari City Regional General Hospital are as follows: phlebitis cases due to infusion in 2021-2023 were 8.0 %, 9.7 % and 1.55 % respectively with normal standards < 1 %, SSI data for 2021-2023 were 7.8 %, 8.6 % and 0.7 % respectively with standards < 2%, while there is no data for UTI, decubitus and VAP. The aim of the research is to evaluate the implementation of standard precautions in preventing and controlling HAIs infections in Kendari City Regional Public Houses in 2024.

METHODS

The type of research used, namely qualitative research with a phenomenological approach, was chosen because it was considered able to help researchers dig up information in depth and describe existing conditions in the field regarding the evaluation of standard precautions in preventing and controlling HAIs infections in Kendari City Regional Public Houses in 2024. Informants are people who can provide the necessary information. The selection of informants in this research was carried out using purposive sampling. The informants in this study were 9 people consisting of the Chair of the PPIRS Committee (IPCO) (1 person), IPCN (1 person), IPCD (1 person), IPCLN Mawar Room (1 person), IPCLN Anggrek Room (1 person), IPCLN Dahlia Room (1 person), IPCLN Amaryllis Room (1 person), IPCLN Azalea Room (1 person) and the Nurses Committee (1 person). This research was carried out in the Inpatient Room of the Kendari City Regional General Hospital. The themes and sub-themes in this research are Standard Precautions in Preventing and Controlling HAI Infections, Implementing Hand Hygiene (washing hands), Using Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), Respiratory Hygiene or Coughing and Sneezing Ethics and Safe Injection Practices. Data collection using the interview method. The data analysis techniques used are source triangulation and method triangulation.

RESULTS

The interview results came from interviews with the nine respondents which were carried out in depth in the form of clarifying the respondents' answers with the questions given which were adjusted to the questions in the interview guide. The answers taken from each respondent for each variable studied are answers that are considered not in line with the HAIs standards that have been determined through Minister of Health Regulation number 7 of 2017. The process of implementing HAIs infection prevention and control at Kendari City Hospital through four of eleven standard precautionary components that must be implemented and adhered to by health workers, namely carrying out hand hygiene and using Personal Protective Equipment (PPE).

Hand Hygiene

Hand hygiene is carried out by washing your hands for 40-60 seconds using soap and running water if your hands are clearly dirty or exposed to bodily fluids or using alcohol in the form of handrub for 20-30 seconds if your hands are not visibly dirty, but this must be alternated with one handwash if you have used handrub six times. a. Five Moments for Washing Hands

Hand hygiene indications are carried out at five moments, namely before contact with the patient, before aseptic procedures, after contact with blood and body fluids, after patient contact, and after contact with the environment around the patient. Interview results show that there are still officers who do not carry out hand hygiene at several moments, such as the following:

"There are five moments that we sometimes forget, especially washing hands before contact with patients, which we always forget because we are in a rush. Hand washing training is usually reminded during morning roll call, in-house training is always carried out for new and old employees. always reminded." (ipcln icu)

"for five moments, sometimes you forget, when you are supervised, you just do it" (IPCLN Infectious)

The implementation of the five moments of hand hygiene is carried out during each procedure and after the procedure, and the ones who do it the most are nurses and then midwives. "For patients when they enter, there is always education about the importance of hand hygiene, and they are shown the facilities and places where they are, and the staff always practice it" (IPCN)

"The moment the officer washed his hands he was obedient and there were still some moments that were forgotten, not all moments were carried out" (Head of the Children's Room (Orchid)

"Health workers have carried out compliance moments and are in accordance with standards, all moments are in accordance with the moments" (IPCLN Midwifery room)

Based on observations, five moments of hand washing for nurses on duty at the Kendari City Hospital showed that two of the five indicators of hand washing moments, namely before contact with the patient and before taking action, were moments that were not carried out by nurses, while the other three indicators, namely after contact with blood and body fluids, after contact with the patient and after contact with the environment around the patient, were moments that were always carried out by nurses before taking action.

b. Six Steps to Washing Hands

There are six steps to washing hands according to WHO, namely rub soap evenly on the palms of the hands, rub the back of the hands and between the fingers, rub the palms and between the fingers, the inner fingers of both hands interlock, rub the thumb of the right hand using the left hand and vice versa, finally rub the fingertips of the right hand on the palm of the left hand and vice versa. The interview results showed that all officers carried out six steps for washing their hands, as follows:

"Six steps are very good. "I have used handrub, but sometimes the handrub is empty from the pharmacy, so if it's empty, always wash your hands using running water" (IPCLN ICU)

"The steps are in accordance with the six standard precautionary steps. Handrub is available and always provided for refills, wash basins are also available in every corridor with hand washing soap always provided" (IPCLN Infectious)

"The implementation of the six steps for washing hands is appropriate. evaluate the moment of washing hands, the lowest moment is before contact with the patient which is mostly forgotten, the most frequently done is when carrying out and after carrying out the action. In implementing the provision of facilities, we have parties who back up to provide facilities when one of the supplies runs out. Procurement is through pharmacies, (diapharmacy ampra) the amount of use, dosage depends on need, carried out every 2 weeks" (IPCN)

"The implementation of hand washing is in accordance with WHO. Socialization PPI routinely carries out outreach to officers. "The facilities are available, you can pick it up at the pharmacy at the pharmacy according to a predetermined schedule. There has been an incident where the handrub was not available because it was out of stock for a short period of time" (Head of the Children's Room (Orchid)

"The six steps for washing hands have been practiced by health workers. Availability is always there, by requesting a pharmacy. provision is carried out by the hospital" (IPCLN Obstetrics room)

"The availability of hand washing facilities, soap and so on is always reported if there is a shortage. IPCN is very active. "If there is something lacking, always report it to the group" (Medical Committee (IPCO)

The results of observing the six steps for washing hands showed that three of the six indicators of hand washing steps, namely rubbing the backs of the fingers with interlocking movements, rubbing the right thumb with the left hand and vice versa and rubbing the tips of the right fingers with the left palm and vice versa were not fully carried out. Meanwhile, the other three indicators, namely rubbing the palms with soap, rubbing the palms of the back of the hands and rubbing soap between the fingers, have been fully carried out by nurses at the Kendari City Hospital.

Personal protective equipment

Personal protective equipment or PPE is equipment used by officers to protect themselves from physical, chemical, biological hazards/infectious materials. PPE consists of gloves, masks, protective gowns, goggles and face shields, protective hats and

protective shoes. The results of the interviews explained that the availability of PPE was sufficient but sometimes there were obstacles, such as the following:

"PPE is always used, especially masks and gowns. There is always availability for each room" (IPCLN ICU)

"The use of PPE in the infection room, thank God, all employees are compliant in its use and all the equipment is always available, the estimated supply is every two weeks when stock is expected to decrease" (IPCLN Infectious)

"For PPE, officers are complete and the value reaches 100%, surgical clothing is sterilized, evaluation of the use of PPE is in accordance with the regulations, Minister of Health Regulation No. 27. "And if there are officers who use handsoen that do not comply with standards, they will always be reprimanded, the officers' PPE is always available (sufficient) and if they run out, they will be re-sampled at the pharmacy" (IPCN)

"Everyone has complied with PPE, there is availability in the room, the procurement process is the same as washing hands" (head of the Children's Room (Orchid))

"The implementation of PPE is appropriate and according to standards, PPE is always available, by taking it to the pharmacy and the asset room such as boots, carrying it out twice a week which is taking care of the pharmacy staff, but if availability runs out we can take it directly to the pharmacy ourselves, the pharmacy is always available" (IPCLN Midwifery room)

"Availability of PPE, activities that support services must be supported by management such as providing hand drub, soap, tissue. "If availability has decreased, it must be reported immediately. "Yesterday there was a slight problem regarding the budget at the beginning of the year, including a debt in provision that had not been paid off so it was locked and could not be ordered" (IPCN Committee)

The results of observations regarding the use of PPE by nurses showed that three of the six indicators for the use of PPE had not been implemented by officers, namely Google and face shields, protective hats and protective shoes. Meanwhile, three other indicators, namely gloves, masks and protective gowns, have been implemented by officers before carrying out disease prevention and control measures.

Coughing and Sneezing Etiquette

Steps when coughing and sneezing, namely covering the nose and mouth with a tissue or handkerchief or upper arm, throwing the tissue into the infectious waste bin and then washing your hands. Transmission of viruses from coughing and sneezing which is transmitted via airborne and droplets can be prevented by using a mask. Interview results show that on average officers use masks, as follows:

"Cough etiquette is in accordance with regulations" (IPCLN ICU)

"banners about cough etiquette are in accordance with regulations" (IPCLN Infectious)

"Cough etiquette, health workers have carried out respiratory hygiene cough etiquette steps and we already have rules, the implementation has been carried out because we have provided pamphlets and so on, for patients they are first screened for coughs, if they cough then they are given a mask" (IPCN)

"Implementation of cough etiquette is appropriate and always informed to patients and supported by information provided such as leaflets and so on" (IPCLN Obstetrics room)

The results of observations regarding coughing and sneezing etiquette show that one of the two indicators that have not been implemented by nurses is throwing tissue into the infectious organic waste bin and washing hands, while one indicator that has been implemented is covering the nose and mouth with a tissue/handkerchief/upper arm. Apart from that, officers have used masks during duty hours to prevent HAIs infections.

Safe Injection Practices

Use sterile disposable syringes and needles for each injection, then dispose of used syringes and syringes properly. The interview results show that safe injection practice activities have been carried out 100%, as follows:

"Injecting practice, the officers have used the syringe once, (in accordance with the principles of safe injection), the safety box is always available, if there is a case of being exposed to a syringe, the officer always coordinates with the PPI committee, (there are incidents of officers being injected with needles) and destruction through a third party who is always in contact (IPCN)

"Injecting is safe, syringes are used only once, one syringe is for one type of medicine (after using it, throw it away) a safety box is always available, cases of being exposed to syringes from patients have occurred, the prevention process is carried out by reporting it to the PPI committee and carrying out further examinations" (Head of the Children's Room (Orchid)

"Safe injection practices, the syringe is used once, so one patient one dose at a time, so after use it is immediately thrown away. used every eight hours, safety box is always available, there has never been a case of needle pricks by officers, because we have provided the route" (IPCLN Infectious)

"There have been no wrong injection practices this year. The head of the room usually reports and makes a chronology and then investigates. "Sometimes if something goes wrong, it is always considered normal and ends up not being reported. For the use of syringes, they are used 1 x 24 hours for the same drug, they should only be used once, general evaluation, yesterday's target should have been good for safe injection practices, but there are still people who make mistakes." (IPCN Committee)

Observation results show that officers have carried out safe injection practices, especially in patients who require intramuscular injection. This is to prevent HAIs infections at Kendari City Hospital by using one syringe and one needle per injection and then discarding them in the safety box.

DISCUSSION

Hand Hygiene

a. Five Moments for Washing Hands

The results of research through interviews stated that not all nurses at the Kendari City Regional Hospital had carried out the five moments of washing their hands. This is because there is still a lack of awareness among nurses and this is also due to the rush factor in carrying out actions. The results of this study are supported by the results of observational research which shows that two of the five indicators of hand washing moments, namely before contact with the patient and before taking action, are moments that are not carried out by nurses, while the other three indicators, namely after contact with blood and body fluids, after contact with the patient and after contact with the environment around the patient, are moments that are always carried out by nurses before taking action. Awareness and compliance really need to be carried out by nurses before taking action to prevent and control disease, even though nurses generally know about the importance of implementing the five moments of hand washing.

The results of this study are in line with research [11] regarding the analysis of the implementation of prevention and control of nosocomial infections in the ICU of Labuang Baji Hospital, Makassar, which states that even though nurses know how to wash their hands properly, there are still nurses who do not wash their hands when caring for patients. Apart from that, this research is in accordance with the results of [12] regarding the analysis of the relationship between nurses' behavior towards measures to prevent nosocomial infections (phelibits) in the internal care room at Bima Regional Hospital which stated that the majority of nurses did not wash their hands before carrying out actions or contacting patients. Research [13] on the relationship between the implementation

of infection prevention and control programs on nurses' behavior in preventing and controlling nosocomial infections in the inpatient rooms of Kendari City Regional Hospital stated that the thing that implementing nurses most often forgets before contact with patients is washing their hands before contact with patients.

Based on [5] Concerning Guidelines for Prevention and Control in Health Service Facilities, it states that officers must apply standard precautions to avoid infection, one of which is hand hygiene, namely through five moments of hand washing. Hand hygiene is carried out by washing hands with soap and running water for 40-60 seconds if hands are clearly dirty or have been exposed to body fluids, or using alcohol (alcohol-based handrubs) for 20-30 seconds if hands are not visibly dirty. The results to be achieved in hand hygiene are to prevent infection, colonization of patients and prevent contamination from patients to the environment, including the staff's work environment. According to [14] every time they carry out medical procedures and actions as well as treatment, officers must make it a habit to wash their hands.

Health workers at the Kendari City Regional Hospital have carried out five hand washing moments, but not all officers have implemented it. The moment that is most often not done is before contact with the patient and the moment that is most often done is after contact with the patient. The non-compliance of officers with the five moments of hand washing is due to the lack of selfawareness of each officer in preventing the occurrence of HAIs. Apart from that, non-compliance is also due to officers feeling lazy and not yet making the culture of hand washing a good habit. Facilities and infrastructure are still lacking, such as the lack of availability of sinks, there are still several sinks that are clogged and there is no soap and tissue available, causing officers to only wash their hands using handrub, while for moments after being exposed to body fluids, patients are required to wash their hands using running water and soap.

Apart from that, in some rooms the placement of handrub bottles is not up to the mark, such as at every entrance to the patient's room there must be a handrub bottle, while there are several rooms where handrub bottles are placed only at the entrance to the treatment room, but for the ICU room it is appropriate, namely every patient's bed has handrub. Each installation of a handrub bottle based on observation results is equipped with instructions on how to wash hands properly.

For officers carrying out procedures, handrub bottles should be available in the procedure trolley which makes it easier for nurses to wash their hands before the procedure so that every required moment, such as before touching the patient and before carrying out aseptic procedures, can still be carried out so that there are no longer certain moments where performance is low.

Apart from that, supervision which is only carried out routinely once a month by the PPI team makes some officers negligent and only carry out hand hygiene when being supervised, not because they are aware of the importance of washing hands even though SOPs regarding hand hygiene have been established and socialization has also been frequently carried out by the PPI Team. Therefore, it is hoped that all officers will be able to carry out five moments of hand washing as a good culture in efforts to prevent and control HAIs infections.

Six Steps to Washing Hands

The results of research through interviews show that Kendari City Regional Hospital health workers already know what the six steps are in washing hands, but there are still steps that are missed because they are not implemented often or sometimes they just wash their hands without implementing the six steps that have been determined. These results are supported by the results of observations made, namely three of the six indicators of hand washing steps, namely rubbing the backs of the fingers with interlocking movements, rubbing the right thumb with the left hand and vice versa and rubbing the tips of the right fingers with the left palm and vice versa. Meanwhile, the other three indicators, namely rubbing the palms with soap, rubbing the palms of the back of the hands and rubbing soap between the fingers, have been fully carried out by nurses at the Kendari City Hospital. The six steps for washing hands are one of the basic things before doing anything, especially before taking action to prevent and control disease. This is because if you miss this moment, it will result in an increase in the spread of disease infection in a hospital.

This research is in line with research conducted by [15] which states that the hand washing steps that are most often not done or done but not correctly are the fourth, fifth and sixth steps. The fourth step is to rub the backs of the fingers on the opposite palm, with the fingers interlocked, while the fifth step is to rub the right thumb in a circle inside the palm of the left hand which is in a

clenched position and vice versa. The sixth step, rub the tips of the fingers in the palm in a circular direction towards the axis of the body with the fingers locked in the palm.

The results of research [16] regarding the application of five-moment hand washing with the incidence of nosocomial infections stated that the more often we carry out the correct 6-step hand washing, the less chance of HAI infection occurring, and vice versa. Similar research was also conducted [17] in 2015 with the title compliance with the implementation of hand hygiene activities at Hospital For the implementation of hand washing steps, the percentage of accuracy was only 67%, while for hand washing moments the percentage was 100%. The low accuracy of the steps for hand hygiene activities may be caused by a lack of knowledge among health workers regarding the steps for hand hygiene activities.

Based on [5] Concerning Guidelines for Prevention and Control in Health Service Facilities, it is stated that officers must apply standard precautions to avoid infection, one of which is hand hygiene, namely through the six steps of washing hands.

Health workers at Kendari City Regional Hospital have carried out six steps for washing hands for the specified duration, but not all officers have implemented them. The most frequently performed steps are rubbing the palms, backs, and between the fingers, while interlocking movements, rotating the thumbs, and rubbing the fingertips are rarely done. This is due to the staff's habits and sometimes the patient's emergency condition means that the staff do not have time to carry out the six steps to wash their hands optimally.

Nurses' compliance with six-step, five-moment hand washing at the Kendari City Regional Hospital is influenced by several things, including the existence of six-step, five-moment hand washing education every morning which is followed by all morning shift nurses. Apart from that, regular hand washing audits also influence nurses' compliance in carrying out the six steps and five moments of hand washing. Initially, hand washing audits forced nurses to wash their hands properly according to procedures.

However, over time nurses got used to and complied with the hand washing that was enforced at the Kendari City Regional Hospital.

Apart from that, punctuality has not been achieved properly, where washing hands using alcohol-based handrub should take 20-30 seconds, while washing hands using running water and soap should take 40-60 seconds.

Therefore, it is hoped that all officers will be able to carry out the six steps of washing their hands for the right duration as an effort to prevent and control HAIs infections.

Personal protective equipment

The results of research through interviews stated that nurses always use PPE, especially gloves, masks and gowns. PPE is available, but sometimes there are delays in distributing it to rooms. If this happens, the nurse's solution is to borrow from another room or ask the pharmacy to provide PPE at the hospital. Health workers at the Kendari City Regional Hospital have used PPE in treating patients, but their use correctly and appropriately has not been maximized, such as there are still nurses who do not use Google and face shields and protective hats when handling patients. This is supported by observation results which show that three of the six indicators for the use of PPE have not been implemented by officers, namely Google and face shields, protective hats and protective shoes. Meanwhile, three other indicators, namely gloves, masks and protective gowns, have been implemented by officers before carrying out disease prevention and control measures. The use of PPE for nurses is very important for nurses to carry out and implement when carrying out disease prevention and control measures, this is because having complete PPE will minimize the spread or infection of bacteria from nursing patients.

The results of this research are in line with research [11] regarding the analysis of the implementation of HAIs infection prevention and control in the ICU of Labuang Baji Hospital, Makassar, which states that the personal protective equipment available in the ICU room is: gloves, masks, head coverings, protective clothing and work clothes, as well as protective shoes. Some nurses did not use personal protective equipment according to existing PPE indications. Such as not using masks, head coverings and protective shoes according to the indications that have been explained. It was also found that several nurses still wore office work clothes when going home or leaving the hospital.

Based on [5] Concerning Guidelines for Infection Prevention and Control in Health Service Facilities, it states that personal protective equipment is special clothing or equipment worn by officers to protect themselves from physical, chemical, biological/infectious material hazards. PPE consists of gloves, mask/particulate respirator, eye protection (google), shield/face shield, head covering, protective gown/apron, sandals/closed shoes (boots). The indication for use of PPE is if an action is carried out that may allow the body or mucous membranes to be exposed to or splashed with blood or body fluids or the possibility of patient contamination from staff.

Masks are used to protect the face and oral mucous membranes from splashes of blood and body fluids from patients or dirty environmental surfaces to prevent airborne transmission. Gloves are required when cleaning blood/body fluids and inserting/removing IV drips. Protective gowns are used to protect officers' clothing from possible exposure or splashes of blood/body fluids, secretions, excretions/protect patients from exposure to officers' clothing during sterile procedures. Google and face shields to protect eyes and face from splashes of blood, body fluids, secretions and excretions. Protective shoes are used to protect officers' feet from spills/splashes of blood/other body fluids and to prevent possible punctures from sharp objects/falling medical equipment. Shoes must not have holes in order to function optimally. Protective hats to prevent the fall of microorganisms in the staff's hair and scalp onto equipment/sterile areas/patient mucous membranes and vice versa [5].

Health workers at the Kendari City Regional Hospital already use PPE when treating patients. Officers always wear masks during work hours, gloves are used according to specified indications, such as when inserting/removing IV drips and carrying out dressing changes, protective gowns are used according to specified indications, such as when bathing patients, goggles and face shields are used according to specified indications, such as when installing a CVC, but during observations there are no actions that require the use of goggles and face shields, protective shoes are used by officers, namely in the form of closed sandals, and protective hats are used according to specified indications, such as the act of inserting a CVL, but during observations there are no actions that require the use of a protective hat.

The use of PPE is carried out immediately before carrying out the action and is immediately removed after the action is completed, however, based on the results of observations, it was still found that health workers were still using PPE when the action was completed, such as still using gloves when writing documentation that was used when carrying out treatment procedures for patients. This is also wrong because in this way, we as health workers do not break the chain of HAIs transmission, but instead spread germs through contaminated hands to other objects or objects so that these objects become a means for germs to breed and transfer to other people.

The importance of socializing the use of PPE really needs to be carried out repeatedly to create awareness and habits for health workers. Apart from that, knowledge about the appropriate type of PPE to use when carrying out certain actions must also be possessed by every health worker because not all actions use the same PPE but are adapted to the method of germ transmission that is likely to occur with a particular nursing action.

Many factors influence health workers in using personal protective equipment to ensure their safety before coming into contact with patients and carrying out procedures. It can be influenced by motivation, knowledge, availability of procedures, behavior, habits and the availability of Personal Protective Equipment [18].

Therefore, it is hoped that all officers will be able to use PPE according to the indications, and it is hoped that the management will always provide and distribute PPE on time to each room so that officers can use it when treating patients.

Coughing and Sneezing Etiquette

The results of research through interviews show that health workers at the Kendari City Regional Hospital diligently wear masks during work hours, so that if they cough/sneeze they do not transmit the virus to other people because wearing a mask is one way of preventing infection. Apart from cough etiquette, health workers have carried out respiratory hygiene cough etiquette steps such as covering the nose and mouth with a tissue/handkerchief/upper arm. These results are in line with research findings during observation which showed that one of the two indicators that had not been implemented by nurses was throwing tissue into the infectious organic waste bin and washing hands, while one indicator that had been implemented was covering the nose and mouth with a tissue/handkerchief/upper arm.

The results of this research are in line with research [17] regarding the application of standard precautions as an effort to prevent biological hazards in nursing staff, stating that health workers at Tugurejo Regional Hospital, Semarang, wear masks when coughing/flu. If they do not use a mask, the health workers cover their nose and mouth using a tissue or the inside of their elbow.

Based on [19] regarding Guidelines for Infection Prevention and Control in Health Care Facilities, it is stated that coughing and sneezing etiquette is applied to everyone from staff, patients, to visitors, especially in cases of infection with airborne and droplet transmission types. Health service facilities must provide hand washing facilities such as sinks with running water, tissue, liquid soap, infectious waste bins and surgical masks, because masks can protect patients or airborne surfaces from staff when coughing or sneezing and vice versa.

On average, health workers at the Kendari City Hospital always wear masks during work hours, this is one way to prevent transmission and protect themselves from viruses that are transmitted via airborne and droplets. However, what you need to pay attention to is that when you cough using a mask, the mask you are using must be immediately replaced with a new mask. Likewise, you should pay attention to the use of the mask. If it is dirty or damp, it must be immediately replaced with a new one and a maximum of four hours must be used after it is replaced with a new one.

For officers who are not yet wearing masks, they cover their mouths and noses with their upper arms when coughing or sneezing, but there are still officers who do not cover their mouths and noses when coughing and sneezing. Apart from that, throwing tissues into infectious waste bins and washing hands after coughing and sneezing have not been fully implemented by officers. This is also behavior that does not break the chain of infection transmission, especially transmission via droplets and airborne transmission.

It is necessary to know cough etiquette, because from this we have acted in the process of preventing infection. Maybe when you cough, you will cover your mouth with your palm. Our intentions may be good, but they are not necessarily correct and in fact this method will become a medium for the rapid spread of infection. By closing your palms, you are unknowingly transferring bacteria from your palms to other people through touching or shaking hands. Coughing itself is a symptom or sign that is often experienced by everyone. Either due to the presence of irritants such as smoke, dust, or foreign objects in the respiratory tract, or symptoms of an illness such as influenza, bronchitis, tuberculosis and several other diseases [20,21].

Therefore, it is hoped that officers who cough and sneeze can carry out cough and sneeze etiquette steps because this can prevent transmission of the virus to other people.

Safe Injection Practices

The results of research through interviews stated that health workers at the Kendari City Regional Hospital had used one syringe and one needle per person and for each type of medicine, then the waste was thrown into the safety box. Then there are still nurses who carry out recapping before throwing syringe waste into the safety box and there are still nurses who are pricked by syringes, including practical students. The above is supported by the results of observations made, namely that officers have carried out safe injection practices to prevent HAIs infections at the Kendari City Hospital by using one syringe and one needle per injection then throwing them into the safety box, especially for patients who require intramuscular injection.

Based on the results of research that has been carried out, it shows that safe injection practice activities carried out by health workers at the Kendari City Regional Hospital are much better than the previous year. This is because based on a research report conducted by [13] it was stated that in general, the description of the incidence of needle stick injuries in the Kendari City Regional Hospital was that 42.2% of nurses said that they had experienced needle stick injuries, especially syringes when carrying out injection procedures. Although at the research location there is no specific format regarding documenting incidents of needle stick injuries, so this incident is not documented and does not receive special attention from the hospital. Of the 45 respondents who said that 56% of respondents who had been pricked by a needle were caused by a needle prick, 67% of respondents said they were pricked by a needle while taking medicine and 51% of respondents were pricked when opening/replacing the needle cap.

The results of this research are in line with research [17] regarding the application of standard precautions as an effort to prevent biological hazards in nursing staff, stating that overall at Tugurejo District Hospital, Semarang, the principles in handling sharp instruments are in accordance with the standards used, nurses always use gloves when in contact with needles (syringes for injection) or knives, and only use each needle and syringe once and do not remove the needle after use.

Based on [19] regarding Guidelines for Infection Prevention and Control in Health Care Facilities, it is stated that sterile syringes and syringes are only for single use per injection, this also applies to the use of multidose vials to prevent microbial contamination when the drug is used on other patients, then disposing of used syringes and syringes in the correct place, and applying aseptic technique to prevent contamination of injection equipment.

Health workers at the Kendari City Regional Hospital have implemented aseptic technique and used sterile disposable syringes and syringes for each injection and then disposed of the used syringes and syringes in the safety box.

CONCLUSION

Hand hygiene has not been fully implemented by nurses in accordance with the 5 moments and 6 steps for washing hands. The use of PPE has been fully implemented by nurses, especially in the use of masks and gloves during service. Coughing and sneezing etiquette has not been fully implemented by nurses because nurses have not thrown tissues into infectious waste bins. . Injection practices have been fully implemented by all staff, such as applying aseptic technique and using sterile disposable syringes and needles for each injection

REFERENCES

1. Kementerian Hukum dan Hak Asasi Manusia RI, 2009. *Undang-Undang RI Nomor 44 Tahun 2009 Tentang Rumah Sakit*, Indonesia. Available at: www.depkes.go.id.
2. Kementerian Kesehatan Republik Indonesia. *Peraturan Menteri Kesehatan R.I. Nomor 012 Tahun 2012 tentang Akreditasi Rumah Sakit*. Jakarta:Pemerintah. 2012
3. Komisi Akreditasi Rumah Sakit, 2012. *Instrumen Akreditasi Rumah Sakit Standar Akreditasi Versi 2012 1st ed.*, Jakarta: Komisi Akreditasi Rumah Sakit.
4. Nugraheni, R., Suhartono dan Winarni, S. Infeksi Nosokomial di RSUD Setjonegoro Kabupaten Wonosobo. *Media Kesehatan Masyarakat Indonesia*, Vol.11/No.1, April 2012.
5. Peraturan Menteri Kesehatan Republik Indonesia Nomor 27 Tahun 2017 Tentang Pedoman Pencegahan dan Pengendalian Infeksi di Fasilitas Pelayanan Kesehatan.
6. Putri, A.P.S., Artanti, K.D., Mudjiyanto, D., 2017. Bundle Prevention Form Filling Completeness of Surgical Site Infection (SSI) on Sectio Caesarea Patients in 2016. *J. Berk. Epidemiol.* 5, 13. <https://doi.org/10.20473/jbe.v5i1>.
7. WHO. 2011. *Health Profile*. World Health Organization, 561–565.
8. Safira, A, R and Inge D. Infection Prevention and Control (IPC) Program in Hospital. *Journal of Health Science and Prevention Vol 5 No 1 April 2021 – ISSN 2459-919x*
9. Departemen Kesehatan RI. 2008. *Profil kesehatan Indonesia 2007*. Jakarta : Depkes RI Jakarta .
10. Edwardson, S., Cairns, C., 2019, *Nosocomial infections in the ICU*. *Anaesth. Intensive Care Med.* 20, 14–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j>.
11. Sukfitrianty S, Tirmanidhana, F., Raodhah, S dan Bujawati, E. Analisis Pelaksanaan Pencegahan dan Pengendalian Infeksi Nosokomial Di ICU RSUD Labuang Baji Makassar. *Higiene* Volume 4, No. 2, Mei —Agustus 2018.
12. Zulkarnain. Analisis Hubungan Perilaku Perawat Terhadap Tindakan Pencegahan Infeksi Nosokomial (Phlebitis) Di Ruang Perawatan Interna RSUD Bima Tahun 2018. *JISIP*, Vol. 2 No. 1 ISSN 2598-9944 Maret 2018
13. Alifariki, L, O dan Kusnan, A. Hubungan Praktek Menyuntik Aman Dengan Kejadian Cedera Tertusuk Jarum. *Jurnal Perawat Indonesia*, Volume 3 No 3, Hal 229 - 236, November 2019.
14. Darmadi. 2008. *Infeksi Nosokomial: Problematika dan Pengendaliannya*. Jakarta: Salemba Medika.
15. Mera D., Andriani, Y dan Gustinawati. Penerapan Cuci Tangan Five Momen Dengan Angka Kejadian Infeksi Nosokomial. *Prosiding Seminar Kesehatan Perintis* E-ISSN : 2622-2256 Vol. 1 No. 2 Tahun 2018.
16. Susilo, D, B. Kepatuhan Pelaksanaan Kegiatan *Hand Hygiene* Pada Tenaga Kesehatan Di Rumah Sakit X Surabaya. *Jurnal Wiyata*, Vol. 2 No. 2 Tahun 2015.
17. Duwi, B dan Nofita. M. Hubungan Kepatuhan Cuci Tangan Enam Langkah Lima Momen Perawat Dengan Kejadian Phlebitis Di Rsud Dr. Wahidin Sudiro Husodo Mojokerto. *Jurnal Keperawatan* VOL 6 NO 1 (2017)

18. Bayuningsih R. 2010. Breathalyzer For The Hand Washing (Reminding For Hand Washing) Bagi Perawat Di Ruang Icu. *Ilmu Keperawatan*,2: 11-13
19. Permenkes RI, 2017, Peraturan Menteri Kesehatan Republik Indonesia Nomor 27 tahun 2017 tentang Pencegahan dan Pengendalian Infeksi di Fasilitas Pelayanan Kesehatan, Jakarta:Departemen Kesehatan Republik Indonesia.
20. Sahputri J, Sofia R. Penyuluhan Protokol Kesehatan Era Pandemi Coronavirus Disease (Covid-19) di SDN 14 Muara Dua Kota Lhokseumawe. *Lentera (Jurnal: Sains, Teknologi, Ekonomi, Sosial dan Budaya)*. 2020;4(4).
21. Raodah R, Handayani L. Literature Review: Edukasi Perilaku Hidup Bersih dan Sehat (PHBS) Sebagai Upaya Pencegahan Penularan COVID-19. *VISI KES: Jurnal Kesehatan Masyarakat*